

CRACKING BEHAVIOUR AND LIFETIME PREDICTABILITY OF P558 STEEL IN ANNEALED AND COLD DEFORMED STATES UNDER MIXED COMPLEX LOADING

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Samples were cold deformed at 5% and 10% strains before being subjected to simultaneous loading of static compressive stress (250 MPa) and different shear stress amplitudes, $\Delta\gamma_{yx}$ (in terms of 5°, 10°, 15° and 20° angles of twist). Pure torsion cyclic fatigue was also carried out as a reference, with the same $\Delta\gamma_{yx}$ but without the static compressive stress. Furthermore, samples with 250 and 350 MPa static compressive stress and the same $\Delta\gamma_{yx}$ listed above were also tested without cold deformation.

The low shear stress amplitude samples fail in mode I, the high amplitude samples fail in mode II while the mid-range (10° and 15° angles of twist) fail in mixed mode. The static compressive stress seems beneficial for the low $\Delta\gamma_{yx}$ since their application results in a 2-fold and a 4-fold increase in fatigue life for the non-cold-worked and cold-worked samples respectively. In the high $\Delta\gamma_{yx}$ experiments, the static compressive stress results in a reduction of fatigue life. We also see a stress effect here, where 350 MPa results in much more reduction than the 250 MPa. The cold deformation helps herein to offset the negative effect of the static compressive stress.

Critical plane predictions using Smith-Watson-Topper and Fatemi-Socie models gave mixed results signifying that a single model is not sufficient to predict which planes the cracks will be initiated and/or will propagate. This is especially difficult for the mid-range $\Delta\gamma_{yx}$ where crack branching occurs, both models seem unsuited in these situations.

Keywords: Multiaxial fatigue, Critical Plane, Cold working, Life prediction

INTRODUCTION

In typical scenarios, mechanical components undergo intricate fatigue loadings, resulting in multiaxial stress conditions at critical points. Over the past six decades, researchers have dedicated significant efforts to comprehensively explore the challenges of multiaxial fatigue assessment. The goal has been to furnish engineers with reliable methods for predicting fatigue life when confronted with intricate stress states. Due to the inherent complexities of fatigue crack initiation and growth, there is not much success in finding fatigue life prediction techniques that can handle multiaxial loading in different loading conditions and for different materials. There exist mainly strain-based, stress-based, energy-based, and critical plane-based models. The critical plane model is most popular since it often demonstrates good correlation with experimental fatigue data, in addition to being relatively easy to understand and implement. However, in cases where crack initiation and

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propagation are not straightforward and where the loading condition is predominantly tensile or compressive, the accuracy of these models can be limited.

The impact of mean axial load effects on torsional lives can be advantageous, detrimental, or potentially inconsequential. This outcome is contingent upon factors such as the material properties, crack trajectory, shear range, and the level of normal stress.

Moghaddam et al. [1] investigated the effect of contact pressure on torsion fatigue with the aim of simulating failure conditions in rolling contact fatigue of bearing steels. In their study, both experimental and FEM approaches were used to study the effects of contact pressure on torsion. They observed that the application of contact pressure reduced fatigue life significantly especially in the high-cycle region. In the low-cycle regime, different results were reported by Mazelsky et al. [2], where superimposition with static compressive stresses in aluminium 2024-T351, stainless steel 347, and beryllium copper 25 all resulted in increased fatigue life. They linked the effect of superimposition with static compressive stresses to hydrostatic stresses.

Recently, Meggiolaro et al. [3] observed mixed results in Al 7075-T651 alloy with detrimental effects in the high shear strain amplitudes (0.69%) where axial cracks were initiated instead of transverse cracks in pure torsion at the same shear strain amplitudes. On the other hand, beneficial effects in the lower strain amplitude region (0.5%) by preventing the initiation of Mode I crack were realised, the lower shear stress amplitude was also insufficient to induce Mode II crack as was formed in pure torsion sample with same shear stress amplitude, hence no crack was detected.

Further beneficial effects were observed by Bemfica [4] where in 304L stainless steels, at 0.35% equivalent strain amplitude, a static compressive stress of -50 MPa resulted in nearly a 13-fold increase in fatigue life as compared to a static tensile stress of 50 MPa. Zhang and Akid [5] likewise in addition to the increase in the fatigue crack initiation life, also noted a stress-level effect: When the compressive stress was raised from -300 MPa to -600 MPa, a 2-fold increase in fatigue life was noted.

Crack initiation and branching seem to have a very great influence on the fatigue life of the materials. This is mainly dictated by the fact whether the material initially cracks in a ductile manner or a brittle manner. Ductile materials often show considerable growth in Mode II (in-plane shear) before progressing into Mode I (tensile or opening mode). While for brittle material fracture happens instantly under Mode II. However, this transition in ductile materials from Mode II to Mode I might not happen since certain materials can exhibit a blend of brittle and ductile behaviours [6]. Furthermore, the crack initiation and propagation mechanism may be dependent on the shear ranges, therefore tensile-driven cracks could be initiated during the high-cycle regime, even under relatively low shear strain ranges, or shear-driven cracks for shorter initiation lives under higher shear strain ranges.

Liu et al. [7] noted that, for high strain amplitude experiments (on coarse-grained copper), the crack branching is directly associated with the applied strain amplitude. High-strain experiments resulted in cracks that deviated perceptibly from the plane of maximum normal stress. Low amplitude experiments, however, demonstrated that the magnitude and/or type (whether tensile or compressive) has no effect in the crack bifurcation direction.

Xu et al. [8] showed that low shear ranges initiated axial mode II cracks that always branched. Static axial tensile stresses necessitated the early branching (viz. short axial cracks). For transverse shear cracks, static axial tension was found by Bonniot et al. [9] to postpone the kinking, which is attributed to friction effects at the crack tip. However, transverse shear cracks branch earlier when static compressive stresses are applied [10].

Machining and treatments, such as shot peening and welding, can also induce prehardening and residual stresses. To be able to do fatigue life predictions accurately under these conditions, an understanding of a material's prior stress history and its deformation behaviour is therefore important. Kpodekon, [11] reported that cyclic softening followed by cyclic hardening is observed for the virgin specimens while only cyclic softening is exhibited by the pre-hardened specimens. Based on their results, the researchers concluded that pre-straining strongly influences fatigue life in that under stress control, it seems to have a positive effect but disadvantageous on the other hand for strain control experiments, this was the case despite compressive mean stress being present.

Belattar et al. [12] while experimenting on 304L and 316L steels, showed that cyclic pre-work hardening has a beneficial effect on life under imposed stress (multiplication factor of 30 for a test under ± 237 MPa after cyclic pre-hardening under 30 cycles at ± 423 MPa) and a detrimental effect on the life at imposed strain, even in the presence of residual compressive stress i.e. greater than a factor of 150 with positive residual stress while it is greater than 9 with a negative residual stress ranging from -150 MPa to -30 MPa.

Haddar [13] studied the effects of cyclic prework (16 cycles at $\pm 1\%$) and monotonic prework (tension up to a true stress of 500 MPa) on the behaviour and service life of a 304L steel in isothermal fatigue at 165°C and in anisothermal fatigue at imposed deformation. It appears that there is no significant difference between the lifetimes of the virgin material and those of the pre-worked material.

Following imposed stress fatigue tests on Al 7050- T7451, without pre-straining and with monotonic pre-straining at 1%, 3%, 5%, and 7%, [14] found a reduction in service life that increased with the level of pre-straining. Microscopical observations by the researchers revealed that pre-hardening facilitates the formation of microstructures characteristic of fatigue, such as persistent slip bands, which lead to a reduction in service life.

Colin et al. [15] observed that pre-straining led to a significantly shorter life in strain-controlled tests, but a significantly longer life in load-controlled tests, as compared with the virgin material. Due to significant hardening and strong deformation history effects, they proposed that a fatigue life parameter (in their case the Fatemi-Socie parameter) which has both stress and strain terms is needed for the correlation of data for a material with deformation history effects like the 304L stainless steel they investigated.

This work seeks to relate the surface crack orientations to the fatigue life of pure torsion, and cyclic torsion with superimposition of static compressive stress (with and without pre-straining) of an austenitic stainless steel with high interstitial nitrogen and low nickel amounts.

EXPERIMENTAL METHODS

Preparation of specimen

The test utilised P558 (DIN 1.3808) austenitic stainless steel sourced from voestalpine BÖHLER Edelstahl GmbH & Co KG. The chemical composition was determined through optical emission spectroscopy, revealing the following composition in weight percentages: C = 0.2, Cr = 17.12, Mn = 12.10, Ni = 0.02, Mo = 2.89, N = 0.51, others = 0.45, and Fe = balance. To eliminate any manufacturing process effects, the test bars underwent solution annealing at 1150°C for 45 minutes, followed by quenching in water.

From the solution annealed bars, three types of specimens were machined for specific tests:

1. Eight cylindrical solid specimens, with geometry detailed in Figure 1, were prepared for multiaxial fatigue testing. ($\sigma_{\text{stat}} = -350$ MPa and -250 MPa).
2. Four specimens with the same geometry as Figure 1 were machined for pure torsion fatigue testing ($\sigma_{\text{stat}} = 0$).
3. Eight cylindrical solid specimens, same as those in (1) but were cold deformed to 5% and 10% tensile strain before multiaxial fatigue testing. ($\sigma_{\text{stat}} = -350$ MPa and -250 MPa).

The outer surface of the gauge length of each specimen underwent grinding and polishing to eliminate scratches and rough machining marks, achieving a surface roughness (Ra) of approximately $0.1\mu\text{m}$.

The work-hardened samples were pulled monotonically using a specially designed fixture on a universal tensile machine (Schenk RM100). For our tests, four specimens were cold worked up to 5 % strain and four specimens by 10 % strain. A strain hardening of 5 % and 10 % measured using an extensometer resulted in an elongation of approximately 1.5 mm and 3 mm respectively. The elongation was started and stopped manually at the desired value. Pulling the sample created a rough surface on the entire bar, which was then ground and polished in several stages to eliminate stress concentration points.

All the tests were carried out on the servo-hydraulic machine "Bionix 858 Test System" (MTS, Eden Prairie, USA). The machine can simultaneously support compression loads up to 50 kN in addition to torsional moments of up to 300 Nm. The test system was controlled using an associated software and the measurement data was recorded on the computer. The software also enables the measured values to be displayed graphically and numerically in real-time so that the experiment can be followed on the monitor.

RESULTS

Fatigue life and surface crack morphologies

Table 1 shows the cycles to failure for all experiments i.e., pure cyclic torsion, cyclic torsion + static compressive stress (250 MPa and 350 MPa), and cyclic torsion + static compressive stress (250 MPa and 350 MPa) in addition to pre working to 5% and 10%. For the low shear stress amplitude i.e. 5° angle, which corresponds to about 300 MPa maximum shear stress, there is an increase in fatigue life by more than 100%. This increase is somehow less when the static compressive stress is increased from -250 MPa to -350 MPa, but it is much higher (more than a 200% increase) when preloading was done before the static compressive stress was superimposed. Further, 10% preloading results in more life than 5% preloading. Looking at the SEM micrograph of the 5° pure torsion sample (Figure 1a), a mode I crack can be observed with a mode II branch. It is believed that the superimposition with compressive stress hinders the mode II branching (compare with Figures e and i).

In almost all the other instances (except for -250 MPa superimposition with 10% preload), the superimposition with compressive stress and preloading is detrimental to fatigue life. Particularly with the higher shear stress amplitude (20° angle of twist which corresponds to $\tau_{\text{max}} = 500\text{-}575$ MPa) and with a high compressive stress (i.e., 350MPa), there is a 95% reduction in life. However, it seems like preloading is beneficial in offsetting this detrimental effect of the static compressive

stress, and the greater the level of preloading, the more the offsetting effect is. However, since preloading was done up to 10% strain, it is not known how much preloading is beneficial.

TABLE 1 Fatigue life for pure torsion (PT), torsion with static compressive stress, and with preworking (CD).

Static stress (MPa)		Angle of twist (degrees)			
		5	10	15	20
0 (PT)	Cycles to failure	596793	52810	20262	4596
	% Change from PT	0	0	0	0
-250	Cycles to failure	1400000	45375	8776	2775
	% Change from PT	135	-14	-57	-40
-350	Cycles to failure	1200000	19200	7276	244
	% Change from PT	101	-64	-64	-95
-250 with 5%CD	Cycles to failure	1898609	47857	11855	4135
	% Change from PT	218	-9	-41	-10
-250 with 10%CD	Cycles to failure	2000000	43112	11247	4849
	% Change from PT	235	-18	-44	6

Figure 1j, k, and l show that for this high shear stress amplitude, with or without static compressive stress or preloading, horizontal and vertical oriented cracks are formed (since the specimen's longitudinal axis is horizontal, these are therefore axial and transverse axes respectively). The reduction in the fatigue life with the superimposition of static compressive stress is believed to be because of the deviatoric compressive stresses. At these high shear stress amplitudes, there are deviatoric stresses that could cause the tensile cracks to close (rub against each other) thereby reducing failure. As shown in figure 1a, b, and c, tensile cracks ($\pm 45^\circ$) occurred for low shear stress amplitudes ($\tau_{max} < 300$ MPa) irrespective of whether there was a static compressive stress, or a pre-straining done. Furthermore, it is to be seen that superimposition with static compressive stress results in an increase in fatigue life (more than two times) when a 250 MPa compressive stress is superimposed.

FIGURE 1 Surface crack morphologies for pure torsion (first column), cyclic torsion with static compressive stress without preload (second column), and cyclic torsion with static compressive stress with 250 MPa preload (third column). The rows represent the experiments with same angle of twist.

For the higher applied amplitudes ($\tau_{max} = 500$ to 575 MPa), the superimposed static axial compression had a detrimental effect on the shear cracks formed. Firstly, the sample without static stress superimposition (i.e. pure torsion), had axial and transverse cracks (horizontal and vertical respectively). However, with superimposition with static compressive stress, the growth and

propagation of the transverse crack is made difficult by the static compressive stress i.e., they closed up, but axial cracks propagate more quickly since the deviatoric stresses occurring perpendicularly to the cracks open the cracks up leading to faster failure.

Critical plane predictions

The comparison between predicted and observed crack orientations for the two models is shown in Figure 2. Since more than one plane may experience fatigue damage in the same manner as the maximum critical plane, CP_{max} , a range rather than a single plane was defined. In this work, this range is $CP > 0.9 CP_{max}$ defined without a justification rather taking note that errors may have been accrued with fitting the data of the Fatemi-Socie Model and the Smith-Watson-Topper (SWT) Model. Furthermore, it is important to point out that there are discrepancies between how different authors defined the critical plane in the Fatemi-Socie Model. Some define it as the plane with the maximum shear strain amplitude, while others on the other hand define it as the plane with the maximum damage parameter D .

Figure 2 shows that for pure torsional fatigue samples, the Fatemi-Socie model (Figure 2a) is poor in predicting the low shear stress amplitude sample (5° angle of twist) as one would expect since the sample fails under mode I ($\pm 45^\circ$) while the model predicts ranges between -90° to -70° , -20° to 0° and at 90° . On the other hand, in the high amplitude sample (20° angle of twist), the model predicts the crack orientation direction somewhat accurately. In the mid-range shear strain amplitude experiments (i.e. 10° and 15° angle of twist), the model predicts cracks oriented near the 0° , 90° and -90° angles but the actual angle orientations are axial cracks (0°) with branches ($\pm 41^\circ$ for the 15° angle of twist and $\pm 37^\circ$ for 10° angle of twist). It is evident here that the prediction of the FCI lives is made difficult by the fact that one cannot predict whether branching or kinking will or will not occur. Figure 2b, SWT model prediction for torsional fatigue sample, predicts the low amplitude experiments. It shows that cracks should initiate and/or propagate along the $\pm 35^\circ$ to $\pm 55^\circ$ planes wherein the $\pm 45^\circ$ planes that define Mode I cracks lie. It fails to predict the axial cracks (0°) and transverse cracks ($\pm 90^\circ$).

Figure 2c is a graphical representation of predictions of critical planes for multiaxial fatigue by the F-S model in relation to actual crack orientation for the investigated angle of twists (i.e. 5° to 20°). The model seems to perform better as compared to the predictions for pure torsion experiments for the 10° and 15° angle of twist experiments that had mixed mode type of cracks (although not 100% accurate). It is not any better for the 5° angle of twist. It, however, is again accurate to predict the high strain amplitude experiment. The SWT model predicts the cracking mode of multiaxial fatigue samples better than the F-S model except for the high-strain amplitude sample (Figure 2d).

This goes to show that a single damage model may not be sufficient to predict the initiation of shear, or tensile cracks and it becomes more complicated when mixed-mode cracks are available since one can neither predict whether they will or will not form, nor is there a model that captures this cracking behaviour appropriately.

FIGURE 2 Crack orientation predictions vs Angle of twist with Fatemi Socie Model (a and c) and Smith-Watson-Topper model (b and d) for pure torsion fatigue (a and b) and multiaxial fatigue with 250 MPa static compressive stress without pre-straining (c and d).

CONCLUSIONS AND FUTURE WORK

In this study, pure cyclic torsion fatigue and multiaxial fatigue on (cold and non-cold-deformed) P558 Austenitic steel were performed. The following conclusions can be drawn from the research:

1. Prestraining is beneficial under specific conditions, therefore more research should be carried out to determine these optimum conditions. For instance, cold deformation at higher strains e.g. 30% or 40% and subsequent multiaxial fatigue are planned to help shed light on the question: To what extent is cold deformation helpful in increasing the fatigue life especially when static compressive stresses are in play in service?
2. Static compressive stresses as a superimposition to cyclic torsion results in the cycles to failure in the high cycle regime but detrimental in the low cycle region.
3. The effect of stress magnitude is pronounced in the low cycle regime than in the high cycle region.
4. Different crack initiation and propagation mechanism are witnessed depending on the shear stress amplitude.

5. The critical plane models cannot be applied in the whole fatigue life range; therefore, they need a closer investigation, especially for materials with a mixed-mode cracking nature.

More research will follow for the investigated materials, particularly scanning electron microscopy to investigate the microstructure alterations and the damage mechanisms while transition electron microscopy will help us to understand the dislocation activities, slipping and twinning mechanisms, etc.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

The authors would like to thank the Kenyan-German Postgraduate Program facilitated by Deutscher Akademischer Austausch Dienst (DAAD) and Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft (project number 41180620). Furthermore, the authors are appreciative of voestalpine BÖHLER Edelstahl GmbH & Co KG for the provision of the research material.

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